

Naturally occurring "*Sesum indicum*" oil as corrosion inhibitor for zinc in hydrochloric acid

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Abstract : Corrosion behavior of zinc in hydrochloric acid solution was studied using weight loss as well as galvanostatic polarization measurement with and without *Sesum indicum* oil. The percentage inhibition efficiency increases with increasing *Sesum indicum* oil concentration. All the data reveal that the oil acts as an excellent inhibitor for corrosion of zinc in HCl solution. Thermodynamic, kinetic parameters and equilibrium constant for adsorption process were calculated from the experimental data. The adsorption of *Sesum indicum* oil on zinc was found to follow the Langmuir adsorption isotherm at all the concentration study.

Keywords : Corrosion, weight loss, galvanostatic polarization, *Sesum indicum*.

Introduction

Extracts of herbs, species and medicinal plants are used as food additives to provide flavor and other functional properties. Extracts of these plants possess antioxidant and anticancer properties while synthetic antioxidants such as dibutylhydroxy-toluene (BHT) are easily available and effective, but have limitations on their use, because it can also be harmful to human health¹. For this reason naturally occurring antioxidants are usually preferred both to stabilize food products and for use in the pharmaceuticals and cosmetics. *Sesum indicum* oil is known to have antioxidant properties and diets containing these antioxidants can reduce the risk of diseases like cancer and anemia. The diversity of their structures plays a major role in their use as corrosion inhibitor. Generally compounds that contain nitrogen, sulphur and oxygen atoms as well as multiple bonds provide effective corrosion inhibition²⁻⁴. The importance of the study lies in fact that the naturally occurring *Sesum indicum* oil is environmentally compatible, non-polluting, non-toxic, easily available, biodegradable and cheaper corrosion inhibitor. The percentage composition of fatty acid is 44%, stearic acid 4.2%, palmitic acid 9% and arachidic acid 0.7%⁵. The presence of sesamol, sesamin and sesamoline in *Sesum indicum* oil were worked as inhibitor in 0.5 N HCl solu-

tion. The oil adsorbed on the surface obeys Langmuir isotherm. They offered large coverage due to the long hydrocarbon chain and presence of OH group in one of lignan sesamol of *Sesum indicum* oil being hydrophilic in nature and ensured the solubility⁶. In the present paper our aim is to study the inhibition effect of *Sesum indicum* oil on the corrosion of zinc in 0.5 N HCl solutions by using gravimetric and electrochemical galvanostatic polarization methods. Chemical structures of few major components of *Sesum indicum* oil are represented as :

Sesamol

Sesamin

Sesamoline

Results and discussion

Table 1 shows the value of inhibition efficiency (IE%), surface coverage (θ) and corrosion rate obtained at different concentrations of the inhibitor in 0.5 N HCl for 3 h immersion period. From the weight loss value, the inhibition efficiency (IE%) and surface coverage (θ) were calculated. It is clear from observed data that the addition of inhibitor to the acid has reduced the corrosion rate. Inhibitor efficiency increases with the concentration of the inhibitor for different immersion times 1, 3, 6, 15 and 24 h.

Table 1. Inhibitor efficiency (IE%), corrosion rate and surface coverage (at room temperature) obtained from weight loss method for zinc in 0.5 N HCl (Immersion time : 3 h)

Concn. of inhibitor (g/lit)	ΔW (g)	IE%	Corrosion rate (mmpy)	Surface coverage
-	0.0250	-	0.055019×10^3	-
1	0.0072	71.22	0.015845×10^3	0.7122
2	0.0065	74.00	0.014305×10^3	0.7400
3	0.0060	76.00	0.013204×10^3	0.7600
4	0.0048	80.80	0.010563×10^3	0.8080
5	0.0033	86.80	0.007262×10^3	0.8680
6	0.0020	92.00	0.004401×10^3	0.9200

Kinetics of zinc corrosion in HCl solution with and without inhibitor :

The corrosion data fit to the rate law for first order rate equation as expressed in equation⁷,

$$\log (W_i - \Delta W_t) = - \frac{k}{2.303} t + \log W_i$$

where k is the first order rate constant, W_i is the initial weight of zinc sample, ΔW_t is the weight loss of zinc sample at time t and the term $(W_i - \Delta W_t)$ is the residual weight of zinc sample at time t and can be designated as W_f . The plots are linear for corrosion of zinc in HCl solution in absence and presence of inhibitor. The values of rate constants obtained from the slope of such plots are presented in Table 2.

The values of half life $t_{1/2}$ were calculated using the equation below⁸.

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{k}$$

Table 2. Kinetic parameters for the corrosion of zinc in varying concentration of *Sesum indicum* oil

Concn. of inhibitor (g/lit)	k (s^{-1})	$t_{1/2}$ (s)
0	13.8×10^{-8}	5.02×10^6
1	4.6×10^{-8}	1.50×10^7
2	4.6×10^{-8}	1.50×10^7
3	2.3×10^{-8}	3.0×10^7
4	2.3×10^{-8}	3.0×10^7
5	2.3×10^{-8}	3.0×10^7
6	2.0×10^{-8}	3.4×10^7

The rate constant k decreases with concentration of inhibitor whereas $t_{1/2}$ increases with increasing concentration of the inhibitor.

The mechanism of corrosion inhibition may be explained on the basis of adsorption behavior of the inhibitors. The anodic reaction of zinc in HCl solution is

Various cathodic reactions can also occur simultaneously on a metal surface as shown below⁹.

The primary step in action of inhibitors in acid solutions is generally adsorption on the metal surface which is usually oxide free in acid solutions. The adsorption of an inhibitor species on the metal surface in aqueous solutions should be considered a place exchanger reaction :

where x , the size ratio, is the number of water molecules displaced by one molecule of inhibitor.

The degree of surface coverage (θ) for different inhibitor concentrations evaluated from weight loss method were tested graphically by fitting to various isotherms. The plot of C/θ vs C shows a straight line. This suggests that inhibitor covers both the anodic as well as cathodic regions through general adsorption following the Langmuir isotherm¹⁰,

$$C/\theta = C + 1/K_{ad}$$

where K_{ad} is the equilibrium constant of adsorption. As the adsorption isotherm in 0.5 N HCl is of Langmuir type with slope of almost unity, monolayer of the inhibitor

Fig. 1. Cathodic and anodic polarization curve of zinc in 0.5 N HCl at various concentration of *Sesum indicum* oil.

species must have been attached to zinc surface without lateral interaction between the adsorbed species. Values of free energy of adsorption ΔG_{ads} of *Sesum indicum* on zinc surface were calculated using equation¹¹,

$$\Delta G_{ads} = -2.303 RT \log (55.5 K)$$

where R is gas constant, T is the temperature and K is the equilibrium constant of adsorption of *Sesum indicum* on the surface of the zinc and 55.5 is the concentration of water in the solution, value of ΔG_{ads} calculated from above equation are recorded in Table 3. The negative values of ΔG_{ads} indicate spontaneous nature of the adsorption pro-

Table 3. Langmuir adsorption parameter for the adsorption of *Sesum indicum* oil on the surface of zinc

Temp. (K)	K_{ad}	Slope	$-\Delta G_{ads}$	R^2
298	1.567	1.021	18.869	0.987

cess and stability of the adsorbed layer on the metal surface. Literature search reveals that with regard to energetic of the adsorption process, two types of adsorption process had been established¹².

Galvanostatic polarization studies :

The polarization behavior of zinc functioning as cathode as well as anode in the test solution is shown in Fig. 1.

The electrochemical corrosion parameters deduced from Tafel polarization such as corrosion current I_{corr} , Tafel constant b_a and b_c , E_{corr} are tabulated in Table 4.

Table 4. Electrochemical polarization parameters for the corrosion of zinc in 0.5 N HCl with and without *Sesum indicum* oil

Concn. of inhibitor (g/lit)	E_{corr} (V)	Tafel slopes (V dec ⁻¹)		I_{corr} (A cm ⁻²)	IE%
		b_c	b_a		
		0.0	-0.979		
1.0	-0.977	3.981	4.323	2.031×10^{-2}	18.46
3.0	-1.015	5.061	6.458	3.436×10^{-3}	86.21
5.0	-1.032	8.156	11.79	3.355×10^{-4}	98.65

A decrease in the corrosion current and increase in the cathodic and anodic Tafel slope have been observed with the increase in the concentration of inhibitor. It suggests that inhibitor inhibits corrosion of zinc in acid solution by blocking active sites of zinc surface which in turn decreases the dissolution reaction rate. Since both the anodic and cathodic processes are polarized considerably, E_{corr} values have not changed significantly with the addition of inhibitor suggesting inhibitor is of mixed type

however anodic inhibition is predominating as observed from anodic Tafel slope¹³. The inhibition efficiencies determined from the values of corrosion current are found to be in good agreement with those obtained from weight loss measurements.

Experimental

Rectangular zinc specimens of the composition 1.03%Pb, 0.04%Cd, 0.01%Fe, and the remaining Zn, procured from HZL-Udaipur and size 3 × 2 × 0.2 cm were used for weight loss method. These strips were given mechanical polishing with fine emery paper degreased with acetone before use. After washing, they were dried in oven at 60 °C for about half an hour and cooled to room temperature and weighed. The process was repeated for a constant weight. Each coupon was suspended by a glass hook immersed in a beaker containing 50 ml test solution for different immersion time. Later, the test coupons were cleaned with distilled water and then dried and finally weighed to evaluate weight loss. The corrosion rate in milli miles per year can be obtained by the following equation,

$$\text{Corrosion rate (mm/yr)} = \frac{87.6W}{\rho At}$$

where W is the weight loss (mg), ρ is the density of the specimen (g cm^{-3}), A is the area of specimen (square inch) and t is the exposure time (h). The percentage inhibition efficiencies by the weight loss method are calculated as,

$$\text{IE\%} = \left[1 - \frac{W_1}{W_2} \right] \times 100$$

where W_1 and W_2 are the weight losses (g) for zinc in the presence and absence of additives respectively in HCl solution. The degree of surface coverage (θ) is given by the equation¹⁴,

$$\theta = 1 - \frac{W_1}{W_2}$$

Galvanostatic polarization measurements :

Electrochemical polarization study was carried out in 500 ml glass cell having three electrode system assembly. Galvanostatic polarization of the working electrode

was carried out using an Electrochemical Analyzer CH 6012B. The working electrodes were zinc and platinum used as counter electrode or an auxiliary electrode. The tip of luggin capillary was kept very close to the working area of the electrode and this distance (1 cm^2) was kept constant during the whole study. The specimen was left in the test solution until a constant open circuit potential (OCP) was attained. Experiments were carried out in absence and presence of inhibitor. In the case of polarization method the inhibitor efficiency (IE%) is calculated as :

$$\text{IE\%} = \left(1 - \frac{I_{\text{corr}}}{I_{\text{corr}}^0} \right)$$

I_{corr}^0 and I_{corr} are the uninhibited and inhibited corrosion current densities respectively determined by Tafel line to corrosion potential.

Conclusions :

Sesum indicum oil acts as an excellent corrosion inhibitor in 0.5 N HCl solution. The inhibition efficiencies of almost 98% in 0.5 N HCl have been obtained with a small amount of *Sesum indicum* oil (5 g/lit. HCl) by weight loss technique at room temperature. The inhibition efficiency value obtained from weight loss studies and galvanostatic polarization measurements showed fairly good agreement.

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